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**Parliaments' ex-post oversight of the Covid-19 crisis
governance:**

The formation of ad hoc Covid-19 committees

**WP3: The Making and Breaking of Rules in Crisis Situations:
The Rule of Law and Democratic Participation**

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Executive summary¹

Much debate on the legitimacy and democratic quality of Covid-19 crisis governance has centered on the weakening of parliaments' power. During the evolution of the crisis and with its end, particularly parliamentarian representatives of radical right populist parties are demanding a review of Covid-19 crisis governance. This study delves into parliaments' ex-post oversight of Covid-19 crisis governance, with a particular focus on the formation of ad hoc Covid committees. It suggests that the performance of crisis governance, parliaments' role, populist radical right parties and institutional rules influence the formation of ad hoc Covid-19 committees. To empirically evaluate these propositions, this study systematically examines the creation of legislative ad hoc committees related to Covid-19 governance by the European Parliament, 33 state-level and 104 regional legislatures of European countries. The findings suggest that ad hoc Covid-19 committees have been frequently established, and that the formation of ad hoc Covid-19 committees is predominantly influenced by institutional rules. The formation of ad hoc Covid-19 committees is associated with the institutionalization of a variety of types of ad hoc committees and a lower required share of parliamentarians' support of the establishment of an ad hoc committee. There is no evidence that the formation of ad hoc Covid-19 committees is related to the stringency of the crisis measures, excess mortality or the limitation of parliaments' roles in Covid-19 crisis governance.

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I. Introduction

A key concern regarding the legitimacy and democratic nature of crisis governance revolves around the redistribution of power from legislatures to executives. During crises, such as the Covid-19 pandemic, governmental operations often transition into crisis mode, leading to limitations on two fundamental aspects of legislative power: direct influence over policymaking and post facto oversight of executive actions (Sieberer, 2011). Scholarship on Covid-19 crisis governance has observed significant variability in the roles played by legislatures in governing the crisis (e.g. Cartier et al., 2020; Diaz Crego and Kotanidis, 2020; Ginsburg and Versteeg, 2021; Kettemann and Lachmayer, 2021; OECD, 2020). Consequently, scholars have begun scrutinizing the sources of the variable range of parliamentary policy making and oversight during the Covid-19 pandemic (e.g., Bolleyer and Salát, 2021; Bromo et al., 2024; Chiru, 2024).

Most of these studies on the role of parliaments in Covid-19 crisis governance have focused on parliaments' ex-ante policy and oversight² power by studying whether and to what extent parliaments were able to formulate or amend emergency law making before its enactment. In contrast to ex-ante oversight, whether and how parliaments have reviewed Covid-19 crisis governance from an ex-post perspective have not yet been systematically addressed by the literature. At the same time, radical right parties such as the AfD in Germany and the FPÖ in Austria loudly demand the review of Covid-19 crisis governance and the establishment of inquiry committees for this purpose. Increasingly, it is acknowledged that radical right populist parties' harsh critic of the Covid-19 crisis governance and their demand to establish Covid-19 inquiry committees are important factors for their mobilization and electoral successes (e.g. Hunger et al., 2023).

This study aims to assess parliaments' ex-post oversight of Covid-19 crisis governance and focuses on legislative ad hoc committees established to review and investigate Covid-19 crisis governance. Such ad hoc commissions have been frequent although they varied with regard to their purpose. Some ad hoc commissions were inquiry commission focusing on cases of mismanagement and even corruption related to Covid-19 crisis management, e.g. the purchase of masks. Other ad hoc commissions were study commissions that aimed to formulate recommendations for future crisis management.

This study provides a systematic overview of ad hoc Covid-19 committees at the EU-level and the national and regional level across Europe and addresses the puzzle of why some legislatures have established ad hoc commissions to review Covid-19 crisis governance and others not. Drawing from

² I use the terms oversight, scrutiny, and control in this study interchangeably as Siefken and Rommetvedt (2021).

the literature assessing and examining parliaments' power and the power of opposition parties within legislatures, it suggests that radical right populist parties in parliamentary opposition drive the establishment of ad hoc commissions with the goal to gain political capital from the Covid-19 pandemic. In addition, I expect that ad hoc committees are more likely established when they encounter fewer institutional barriers and when these committees wield greater opportunities that oppositional parties can use.

To evaluate these hypotheses, the article relies on novel data collected on legislative ad hoc Covid-19 commissions established by the European Parliament, the state-level legislatures of 33 European countries, the 98 regional legislatures of Austria, Belgium, Germany, Italy, Spain, Switzerland and the UK, and the 6 legislative bodies of autonomous communities and regions of France, Finland, Denmark, and Portugal.

The descriptive findings of this study highlight that ad hoc Covid-19 committees have become a frequent feature of legislative ex-post oversight of Covid-19 crisis governance and not only at the national but also at the EU- and regional level. According to the results of the analysis, the formation of these committees is mainly driven by the institutional rules related to ad hoc committees and are not related to the presence of radical right populist parties in the opposition. Furthermore, there is a lack of evidence that such ad hoc Covid-19 committees were mainly formed if Covid-19 crisis governance involved more stringent measures or limited the role parliaments more. Furthermore, the results do not sustain that the formation of these committees is associated with worse outcome of crisis governance in terms of deaths.

Thus, this article makes a several contributions. First, contributes to our understanding of democratic quality and legitimacy during the Covid-19 crisis governance by focusing on parliamentary oversight. With its focus on ex-post oversight and review of Covid-19 crisis governance, systematic mapping of ad hoc Covid-19 committees and analysis of the formation of ad hoc Covid-19 committees, it fills an important gap in the literature on parliaments in Covid-19 crisis governance.

Second, it advances the field of legislative oversight by systematically detailing the characteristics of ad hoc committees, which are often overlooked in studies focusing on parliamentary power and the legislative influence of the opposition (Garritzman, 2017; Wegman, 2022). To my knowledge, ad hoc committees have so far not been systematically analyzed. Consequently, this study provides new cross-national knowledge on the institutional features of ad hoc committees that allows the analysis of the determinants of the formation of such committees. The Covid-19 pandemic provides a unique comparative framework for such an analysis, as all European countries were affected and implemented responses. Moreover, this study enhances the research on legislative bodies in multi-level systems by

including regional parliaments into the analysis. Systematic research on the institutional features of regional parliaments including their committee systems is sparse.

The structure of this paper is as follows: the next section discusses the current state of research on parliaments in Covid-19 crisis governance. Following that, hypotheses on the establishment of parliamentary ad hoc Corona committees are developed in the third section. The fourth section outlines the research design, while the fifth section presents a descriptive analysis of legislative ad hoc Covid-19 commissions across Europe. The sixth section offers the results of an analysis of the establishment of legislative ad hoc Covid-19 commissions and discusses the institutional features of the established ad hoc Covid-19 committees. Finally, the last section summarizes the findings and provides an outlook on future research directions.

II. Parliaments and the Covid-19 crisis governance

The implementation of social distancing measures during the Covid-19 pandemic posed a significant challenge to the functioning of legislatures worldwide. In response, many legislatures had to devise organizational strategies and adopt new technological tools to facilitate the continuation of their work. Scholars such as Diaz Crego and Kotsanidis (2020), Griglio (2020), and Pedersen and Borghetto (2021) have documented these efforts, highlighting the formulation of measures and the implementation of virtual platforms for plenary and commission meetings.

Waismel-Manor et al. (2022) conducted a comprehensive study examining the extent of legislative activities and the utilization of technological solutions to ensure continuity across 159 countries during the Covid-19 pandemic. Their findings revealed that the level of legislative activity and reliance on technical solutions varied significantly depending on factors such as the strength of the legislature and the composition of the government. Specifically, legislatures demonstrated higher levels of activity and increased reliance on technological solutions in cases where they wielded greater power and when governments comprised multiple parties.

The ability of legislatures to oversee responses to the Covid-19 crisis hinged significantly on whether governments declared a state of emergency and the nature of the emergency declaration. In certain countries, when governments declared a state of emergency, legislatures were required to approve this declaration. Additionally, sunset clauses were implemented to ensure that legislatures had to support any extensions of the state of emergency (Griglio, 2020; Lozano et al., 2023).

Parliamentary plenums and committees possess a range of mechanisms to exercise oversight. Once legislatures established methods to maintain their operations, parliamentarians could leverage these

oversight instruments to monitor and regulate governments' emergency law-making in response to the Covid-19 crisis. For example, during plenary sessions, Members of Parliament (MPs) engaged with governments' emergency actions through government statements and by posing questions in the plenary amid the pandemic (Griglio, 2020; Siefken, 2023).

In addition, parliamentary committees played an important role in monitoring executives' emergency law-making. In Finland, the Constitutional Law Committee oversees the constitutionality of bills before they enter into force. In Norway, a special committee was created to consider urgent matters in March 2020 (OECD, 2020: 11). The committee included the President of the Norwegian Parliament and one MP from each of the nine parliamentary groups. In Austria, the Main Committee of the National Council, in which all political parties are represented proportionally to their number of MPs, received an important role from September 2020 onwards (Stöger, 2021: 11). To accommodate oppositional parties and their critic of the weakening role of the parliament during the crisis, a compromise was agreed upon in September 2020. Accordingly, any ordinance by the Federal Minister of Health which is based on the Covid-19-Measures Act and contains a ban on entering certain indoor or outdoor premises or decrees a stay-at-home order would now on require the consent of the Main Committee. This compromise was rather symbolic as the government parties commanded a majority in this committee so that the Main Committee always gave its consent to the measures. MPs of oppositional parties could however voice their critic by not always giving their consent to these measures.

Another important aspect of legislative oversight during the Covid-19 pandemic that received relatively a lot of attention was legislatures' power to oversee the budgetary aspects of executives' and the EU's Covid-19 emergency measures (Griglio, 2020; OECD, 2020). For example, in Austria a special subcommittee of the Budget Committee responsible for parliamentary oversight and control of Covid-19 measures was created. This subcommittee was created due to parliamentarians' critics over a lack of transparency in the government's emergency response (OECD, 2020: 11).

In contrast to the extant literature, this study focuses on ex-post parliamentary oversight of the Covid-19 crisis governance. More specifically, it focuses on the establishment of non-permanent committees to review the Covid-19 crisis governance and investigates factors that explain the establishment of such committees.

III. Explaining the establishment of legislative ad hoc Corona commissions

Parliamentary oversight is exerted both by the plenum and committees. While parliaments' standing orders and organizational regulation are highly specific about the permanent committees that need to

be established, regulations of non-permanent or so-called ad hoc committees are often less specific. (Mattson and Strøm, 1995: 259). Ad hoc committees are often referred to as special committees. The standing orders and regulations of parliament sometimes specify different types of special committees.

The two most common types of ad hoc committees are inquiry and study committees. Inquiry committees are non-permanent committees that are formed by a resolution of a parliament to investigate a specific issue. Inquiry committees are therefore an instrument of parliamentary oversight and have wide-ranging of information powers. Usually but not always, their information power exceeds the power of permanent committees. They can summon witnesses or request documents and information from public authorities and the government. Often inquiry commissions are regulated by additional ordinary laws (Pavy, 2020: 11). Inquiry committees usually only consist of the members of the parliament. They only dissolve if their task is completed and a final report is published. Often they formulate numerous recommendations in their final report. They usually only exist during a specific legislative term and often the length of their functioning is restricted to a couple of months. Following a world-wide overview of inquiry committees presented by Yamamoto (2007: 39), the overwhelming majority of parliaments have the authority to establish inquiry committees.

Some of parliaments' standing orders additionally specify another type of special committee that can be set up temporarily. Study commissions usually address novel and complex problems that fundamentally challenge the societal fabric such migration, depopulation, climate change and aging etc. Study commissions often include external experts besides of member of parliament.

While several comparative and single case studies of parliamentary special and inquiry committees exist (Bussjaeger et al., 2016; Pavy, 2020; Rozenberg, 2020; Yamamoto, 2007), they are mainly descriptive. To my knowledge no study has so far investigated the establishment of special parliamentary ad hoc committees from a comparative perspective. In addition, ad hoc committees including inquiry committees are often ignored in studies of oppositional parties' legislative power (Garrizman, 2017). This gap in research is surprising as, committees of inquiry are often considered as the sharpest weapon of parliaments because of their wide-ranging powers and the attention they receive by the media. For example, the House of Representative of the Netherlands considers the right of investigation and inquiry as the parliament's "most powerful instrument"³.

The analysis of the formation of ad hoc committees is particularly insightful in the context of crises, as these committees are designed as tools to address unexpected events and new challenges. Moreover,

³ See the website of the House of the Representatives of the Netherlands: <https://www.houseofrepresentatives.nl/how-parliament-works/democracy-netherlands/duties-and-rights/right-investigation-and-inquiry> (Last accessed 11.04.2024)

the literature on crisis governance widely acknowledges that parliaments are often sidelined by the executive during the initial phase of a crisis. As a result, ad hoc committees are likely used as a mechanism to regain oversight, at least from an ex-post perspective. They also serve as a means to derive lessons for managing future crises. Opposition parties, in particular, may use ad hoc committees to scrutinize the executive's crisis management.

Inquiry committees, as one of the most powerful parliamentary tools, enable comprehensive critiques of government actions. Additionally, special and study commissions provide valuable opportunities for opposition parties to develop expertise and demonstrate their relevance on new critical issues. This dynamic was especially significant during the Covid-19 pandemic, which required unprecedented policy responses and challenged all political parties to articulate coherent positions.

An expanding body of research explores whether and how radical right populist parties capitalize on citizens' frustration and mistrust of Covid-19 crisis governance. Studies have shown that participants in protests against Covid-19 containment measures often exhibit stronger populist attitudes and are more likely to support radical right populist parties (Hunger et al., 2023). Specifically examining attitudes toward face masks and vaccinations, research highlights a polarization, with negative views correlating with populist attitudes and electoral support for radical right populist parties (Jones & McDermott, 2022; Juen et al., 2023; Paul et al., 2021; Wagner & Eberl, 2024). In line with this polarization, the calls by several radical right populist parties for an inquiry commission to review Covid-19 crisis governance align with their broader stance on crisis measures. Thus, I anticipate that radical right populist parties in opposition play a leading role in driving the establishment of ad hoc Covid-19 committees, leading to the formulation of the following hypothesis:

H1: If radical right populist parties are part of the opposition, the likelihood of establishing committees to review Covid-19 crisis governance is higher.

While radical right populist parties might have been most frequently the initiators of the formation of ad hoc Covid-19 committees, the success of their efforts is mediated by institutional regulations. Following the main theoretical proposition of the theory of opportunity structures, permissive institutional rules facilitate the formation of ad hoc committees. Rules that regulate the required share of political support of parliamentarian party groups or a majority of MPs to request and form an ad hoc committee, the number of requests that can be made in a legislative cycle and the number of ad hoc committees that can be established within a legislative cycle shape the likelihood of the establishment of ad hoc committees. Hence, hypothesis 2 examines the effect of the institutional rules

related to the establishment of ad hoc commissions which is the required share of support of parliamentary representatives that is required for their formation.

H2: If the threshold of parliamentary support required to establish an ad hoc committee is lower, the likelihood of establishing such committees to review Covid-19 crisis governance is higher.

Radical right populist parties are likely more motivated to advocate for the creation of ad hoc committees when such committees offer them greater opportunities for influence. Parliaments vary in the extent to which they empower opposition parties to shape policymaking. Committees provide more opportunities for opposition parties when, for instance, they have the right to chair the committee, as the chair often wields significant agenda-setting power (e.g. Garritzmann, 2017). Another key source of influence is the ability of opposition and minor parties to publish alternative minority reports or include dissenting views in the final report of a commission (Mattson & Strøm, 1995; Wegmann, 2022).

In the case of ad hoc committees, representatives from opposition, minor, or radical right populist parties are more likely to invest effort in establishing such committees when more specialized forms, such as inquiry committees or study commissions, are available. Inquiry committees, in particular, are attractive due to their extensive information-gathering powers, while study commissions provide opportunities for representatives to showcase their expertise on topics not yet dominated by the established centrist parties. Reflecting this reasoning, hypothesis 3 formulates an expectation about the impact of the opportunities afforded by ad hoc committees.

H3: If legislative ad hoc committees grant greater opportunities to oppositional parties, the likelihood of establishing such committees to review Covid-19 crisis governance is higher.

IV. Research design

This study aims to explain the formation of parliamentary ad hoc committees that explored issues related to Covid-19 crisis management and governance. Therefore, the dependent variable of the analyses is a dummy variable that takes the value 1 if in a given legislative cycle, a parliament established ad hoc commission aimed at exploring Covid-19 crisis governance. To identify and collect information on ad hoc Covid-19 committees, I consulted parliaments' websites and conducted an

online search in media. I gathered information parliamentary ad hoc commissions addressing the Covid-19 crisis governance established by 33 European countries⁴ and 104 regional legislatures⁵ in legislative cycles that ended after the outbreak of the pandemic as defined by the WHO (11th of March of 2020). In the case of bicameral national legislatures, I included both the lower and upper chambers into the analysis. The analysis only includes ad hoc Covid-19 committees that were requested by MPs and are genuinely new temporary committees. The sample covers the legislative cycles that ended later than 1st of July of 2020 and started not later than 1st of November 2023. These criteria aim to ensure that those legislative cycles are selected in which potentially an ad hoc Covid-19 committee is established.

To analyze the hypothesis, I operationalize their independent variables. To test hypothesis 1, I rely on the variable radical right populist opposition that I operationalize as a dummy variable. It takes the value 1 if a radical right populist party has at least one seat in the parliament and is not fully part of the government during the whole legislative cycle. Accordingly, this variable takes the value 0 if one or more radical right populist parties govern as a senior or junior partner during a legislative cycles or did not manage to gain parliamentary representation in that legislative cycle. The selection of radical right populist parties relies on the classification provided by the PopuList dataset (Rooduijn et al., 2024) (see Appendix C).

As hypothesis 2 proposes an expectation regarding the impact of institutional hurdles to establishing ad hoc committees, the independent variable of this hypothesis is the required support measured by the required share of parliamentary representatives for the establishment of an ad hoc commission. I collected this information relying on constitutional provisions, of parliaments' rules of procedures, laws on inquiry committees and with the support of parliamentary research services.

The independent variable in hypothesis 3 evaluates the opportunities of oppositional parties within ad hoc commissions. The independent variable is the type of ad hoc committees that measure the variety of the institutionalized types of ad hoc committees. It is a dummy variable that takes the value 0 if the standing orders and regulation of a legislature or in case bicameral legislature the lower or upper chamber of a legislature does only allows the formation of ad hoc committees but does not specify its type. It takes the value 1 if either inquiry or study committees are outlined as ad hoc committees.

⁴ These are the 27 EU member countries, Iceland, Liechtenstein, Norway, Switzerland and the UK.

⁵ These are legislatures of the 9 federal states of Austria, 3 communities and 3 regions of Belgium, the autonomous region of Aland in Finland, autonomous region of Corsica in France, 2 autonomous countries of Denmark, 16 states of Germany, 20 regions including the 5 autonomous regions of Italy, autonomous regions of Azores and Madeira in Portugal, 17 autonomous communities and 2 autonomous cities of Spain, 26 cantons of Switzerland and the 3 devolved regions of the UK.

As an alternative measure, I create an index measuring institutional opportunities provided by ad hoc committees. The index is developed drawing on previous studies conceptualizing and measuring oppositional parties' powers in parliamentary committees (for details see Appendix C). It is constructed as an index comprising three components: 1) whether the presidency or the vice-presidency of the ad hoc committee is reserved for an oppositional party; 2) whether an opportunity to publish minority opinion or reports exists; 3) whether the committees meet publicly or behind closed doors.

Additionally, I include four control variables such as the size of the parliaments measured by the number of MPs, the length of the legislative cycle measured by the number of days, a dummy variable that controls for the presence of ad hoc Covid-19 committee in a previous legislative cycle of the same parliament and a dummy variable indicating whether a parliament is a regional parliament.

I conduct two sets of analyses. The first one relies on the full sample of legislatures, while the second one only includes national legislatures to allow for controlling of three characteristics of the Covid-19 crisis. First, I take into account the role of parliaments in Covid-19 crisis governance. It could be that if parliaments had less influence on and oversight of executives' emergency law-making by legislatures, they are more inclined to establish legislative ad hoc commissions to at least oversee Covid-19 crisis governance ex-post.

To assess the impact of parliaments' role in the Covid-19 crisis governance on the formation of ad hoc Covid-19 committees, I calculate the maximum level of legislatures' limitation in Covid-19 crisis governance relying on the data provided by the Pandemic Backsliding (PanDem) project by the V-Dem Institute (Edgell et al., 2020). The PanDem dataset provides observations for five time points (2nd, 3rd and 4th quarters of 2020 and 1st and 2nd quarter of 2021). I created an additive index consisting of three components: (1) the law requires that the national legislature approve the implementation of the legal instrument used as the main national-level response to Covid-19 (emleglaw, 0 yes, 1 no), (2) the legislature has approved the implementation of the legal instrument as the main national response (emlegapp, 0 yes, 1 no) and 3) the extent to which the lawmaking role of the legislature is limited due to any of the emergency measures taken with reference to the Covid-19 pandemic (leglimit, ordinal 0-4). I adjusted the indicator to equalize their weights, ensuring the index ranges from 0 to 3, where higher values indicate a more constrained role of the legislature in governing the Covid-19 crisis. The PanDem dataset excludes countries with small population sizes, such as Estonia, Latvia, Liechtenstein, Luxembourg, Malta and Cyprus.

Second, I control for the stringency of Covid-19 crisis responses as parliaments might be under more pressure to establish ad hoc Covid-19 committees if crisis measures limited individuals' freedoms. To

control for the impact of the stringency of Covid-19 crisis responses, I rely on dataset collected by the Oxford Coronavirus Government Response Tracker (OxCGRT) project (Hale et al., 2021). This Corona response tracker assesses the stringency of a range of policy measures among others for each day between 1st of January 2020 until the end of 2022. Following Engler et al. (2021), I calculate an additive index of the stringency of policy measures composed of the following individual policy response indicators: restrictions on gatherings (0-4), stay at home requirements (0-3), restrictions on internal movement (0-2), international travel controls (0-4). I recalculated the indicators so that additive index ranges from 0 to 4 and the individual indicators have the same weight. I calculated the maximum value of the index.

Third, I control for the severity of the Covid-19 pandemic as a health crisis relying on Eurostat data on the excess death rates. I calculate the maximum monthly excess death rate. Unfortunately, the Eurostat data does not cover the United Kingdom. For legislative cycles during an ad hoc Covid-19 committees has been established, I rely on the maximal values of these three variables considering the time period from 1st of January 2020 and to one month before the first meeting of the ad hoc Covid-19 commission. For legislative cycles without an ad hoc Covid-19 commission, I calculate the maximal values considering the time period from 1st of January 2020 until the start of the respective legislative cycle.

V. Overview of parliamentary ad hoc Covid-19 committees

Since the outbreak of the Covid-19 pandemic and November 2024, all together 49 ad hoc Covid-19 committees have been formed in the legislatures included in the analysis. According to my findings, the European Parliament and the legislatures of 11 countries and 32 regions have established some type of a legislative ad hoc Covid-19 commission (see Appendix A for the list of the established ad hoc Covid-19 committees). In some national legislatures multiple ad hoc committees were created to oversee Covid-19 crisis governance. In France, both the National Assembly and the Senate decided to set up an inquiry commission to investigate government's Covid-19 responses (Derosier and Toulemonde, 2020). The National Assembly also set up a fact-finding mission that later received inquiry powers. In Slovenia, one of the inquiry committees was requested by the governing parties, the other by the oppositional parties. The governing parties blocked the interim report of the inquiry commission requested by the opposition and vice versa. Both inquiry commissions failed to complete and publish a final report. In Spain, the National Congress formed two inquiry committees in different legislative cycles. Furthermore, regional parliaments in the Spanish La Rioja and the Italian region Tuscany have also each formed two ad hoc Covid-19 committees.

All together in relative terms, one third of national legislatures and 31 percent of regional legislature included in the analysis have established a legislative ad hoc Corona commission. These findings show that such committee have been frequently set up underlining the empirical significance ad hoc commissions as a part of ex-post legislative oversight of Covid-19 crisis governance.

The established ad hoc Covid-19 committees differ in several aspects. First, there is variation in the timing of establishment and duration of work among these ad hoc inquiry commissions. For instance, the Covid-19 special commission in Ireland started its work already in May 2020, whereas Italy's Covid-19 inquiry commission gained traction during Giorgia Meloni's radical right populist government in February 2024 (Giuffrida, 2024). The commitment to a Covid-19 inquiry was part of the election campaign promises of the Fratelli D'Italia party, which came into power in October 2022. While Italy's lower house decided to establish an Covid-19 inquiry commission in the summer of 2023 and the senate approved the lower house's decision in spring of 2024, the commission has yet to be convened. In addition, the lower chamber of the Dutch legislature has been only formed in February 2024.

Second, 15 of the 49 ad hoc Covid-19 committees are inquiry committees tasked with investigating the executive's Covid-19 crisis management, 11 ad hoc Covid-19 committees are study committees' and the remaining 13 are generic special committees. In addition, the scope of inquiries conducted by these commissions varies significantly. For instance, the inquiry commissions of Bavaria and Romania both investigated financial irregularities around the public procurement of sanitary materials such as masks. Ad hoc commissions established in several Spanish regions addressed the long-term economic impact of the Covid-19 pandemic and related policy measures. Vaccination plans were the topic of some ad hoc commissions by the legislatures of Italian regions. Similarly, some study and special commissions had a rather narrow focus. However, among all the types of ad hoc Covid-19 committees, we can find some with the task to comprehensively review Covid-19 crisis governance.

Third, looking at the formation of ad hoc Covid-19 committees comparing at the regional with those at the state level, four groups of countries emerge. In Austria and Switzerland, ad hoc legislative Covid-19 commissions were not established at either the federal or regional level. Neither have the national legislatures and legislatures of the autonomous regions of Denmark and Finland established ad hoc Covid-19 commissions. In Germany and Portugal, while no ad hoc legislative Covid-19 commission was established at the federal resp. the state level, several German states established study or inquiry Covid-19 committees, and the legislature of both Portugues autonomous regions established inquiry commissions. In Belgium, Italy and Spain, various Covid-19 commissions were established eventually at both levels. In the UK, both legislative commissions and public inquiry commissions initiated by executives were established at the state and regional levels.

Finally,

VI. Analyzing the establishment of ad hoc Covid-19 committees

In a first step, I test the hypotheses relying on a sample that covers the legislative cycles of the European Parliament, the selected 33 national and 104 regional legislatures that ended later 1st of July of 2020 and started not later than 1st of November 2023. These criteria aim to ensure that those legislative cycles are selected in which potentially an ad hoc Covid-19 committee is established. Furthermore, the sample includes legislative cycles of both chambers in the case of bicameral parliaments.

I estimated hierarchical mixed effects logit models to take into account that regional parliament share a similar national context. Model 1 to Model 4 analyze the independent variables of the hypotheses separately. Then, Model 5 includes all the independent variables together. Finally, Model 6 includes all the independent variables and the control variables.

The results of Models 1, 5 and 6 suggest all that the formation of ad hoc Covid-19 committees is not associated with the presence of radical right populist parties in the opposition. Accordingly, the findings do not support hypothesis 1. Radical right parties are in many European national and regional parliaments harsh critics of Covid-19 crisis governance and as oppositional parties frequently demand the establishment of an inquiry committees to review Covid-19 crisis governance. However, their requests to establish inquiry commissions have often failed. For example, at the federal level, the Freedom Party of Austria (FPÖ) unsuccessfully requested the establishment of a Covid-19 inquiry committee in April 2020 and March 2023, so did the Alternative for Germany (AfD) in September 2022. In Italy, as previously discussed, Fratelli D'Italia is trying to push through the establishment of an inquiry committee after it came to power in 2022. In Portugal, it was also a right-wing populist party, Chega that failed to gain support for its request to establish an inquiry committee. It could be the case that while radical right populist parties more frequently request the establishment of ad hoc Covid-19 committees, they do not succeed because of the lack of support of other oppositional parties. Other oppositional parties usually do not share the fundamental and radical critic of Covid-19 crisis management with radical populist parties. Additionally, in several countries cooperating with radical right populist parties is still perceived as a taboo.

With regard to the influence of institutional hurdles, the results of Model 4 that only includes the required support for the establishment of ad hoc committees, suggest that ad hoc Covid-19 committees are more frequently established if the required support for their establishment is lower. However, when including further independent and control variables, the impact of the required

support does not appear to be significant. These findings do not provide strong evidence to hypothesis 2.

Next, the results from Models 2, 5, and 6 indicate that in parliaments where MPs have the authority to initiate the formation of inquiry committees, ad hoc Covid-19 committees were significantly more likely to be established. In contrast, as shown by Model 3, the authority to establish study committees is not significantly associated with the formation of ad hoc Covid-19 committees. These findings suggest that, unlike the authority to form study committees, the authority to initiate inquiry committees is significantly linked to the formation of ad hoc Covid-19 committees because inquiry committees typically possess stronger informational powers over public administration and the government compared to study committees. Due to these enhanced powers, parties and MPs may be more motivated to invest effort in initiating and participating in the work of ad hoc Covid-19 committees. These results partially support Hypothesis 3. However, when the index of institutional opportunities is included in the model, the findings do not provide additional support for Hypothesis 3.

Table 1: Results of two-level logit regression models of establishment of ad hoc Covid-19 commissions including regional, national and EU-level parliaments

	M1	M2	M3	M4	M5	M6
Radical right populist opposition	0.354 (0.39)				0.243 (0.42)	0.130 (0.47)
Inquiry committee		3.021* (1.20)			2.862* (1.27)	2.994* (1.40)
Study committee			0.233 (0.47)			
Required support				-5.312* (2.42)	-4.850 (2.55)	-5.304 (2.84)
Parliament size						0.004 (0.00)
Past ad hoc Covid-19 committee						-1.530 (0.80)
Regional parliament						0.668 (0.88)
Length of legislative cycle						0.001* (0.00)
Constant	-2.086*** (0.42)	-4.590*** (1.23)	-1.960*** (0.38)	0.420 (1.07)	-2.511 (1.66)	-4.879* (2.15)
<i>Variance component</i>						
Country-level	1.423 (0.93)	1.742 (1.09)	1.405 (0.91)	2.010 (1.25)	2.627 (1.63)	3.692 (2.23)
N observations	285	285	285	272	272	270
N countries	33	33	33	33	33	33
Log-likelihood	-120.7	-115.287	-120.991	-116.311	-112.067	-99.458
Dependent variable: Establishment of an ad hoc Covid-19 committee;						
* p<0.05, ** p<0.01, *** p<0.001, Standard errors in parentheses						

As a robustness check, I conducted the same analysis with the same sample of legislatures excluding upper chambers its composition is determined by other ways than direct elections (see Appendix F). The results of these analyses underline that the presence of radical right populist parties in the

opposition is not associated with the formation of ad hoc Covid-19 committees. They reinforce the findings that parliaments authority to initiate inquiry committees and lower necessary parliamentary support for ad hoc committees are positively and to some extent significantly associated with the establishment of ad hoc Covid-19 committees.

Furthermore, to analyze the impact of radical right populist parties on the formation of ad hoc Covid-19 committees, I estimated the same models, this time including an interaction effect between the presence of radical right populist parties in the opposition and their seat shares. The results indicate that the interaction effect of these two variables is not statistically significant.

As the next step, I analyze whether the characteristics of Covid-19 crisis governance are related to the formation of ad hoc Covid-19 committees, focusing exclusively on a sample of national legislatures. This approach allows for the inclusion of variables that assess the characteristics and outcomes of Covid-19 crisis governance. However, this sampling strategy significantly limits the number of observations. The results indicate that the stringency of Covid-19 measures, the limitations faced by parliaments during the pandemic, the severity of the health crisis and the declaration of some type of a state of emergency are associated with the formation of ad hoc Covid-19 committees. Additionally, the country-level analysis does not suggest that the formation of ad hoc Covid-19 committees is associated with the presence of radical right parties in the opposition or with lower parliamentary support requirements for their establishment.

Notably, 10 out of the 13 ad hoc Covid-19 committees formed by national parliaments are inquiry committees. Consequently, the dummy variable for inquiry committees was omitted from the estimated models, as the lack of parliamentary authority entirely predicts the failure to establish ad hoc Covid-19 committees.

The findings suggest that the authority of parliaments to establish ad hoc Covid-19 committees not only directly influences the formation of inquiry committees but may also incentivize the creation of other types of ad hoc committees. In some cases, it is possible that study or special committees addressing Covid-19 crisis governance were established to preempt the formation of Covid-19 inquiry committees requested by radical right populist parties.

Overall, the findings suggest that institutional rules governing the formation and characteristics of ad hoc committees significantly influence the establishment of ad hoc Covid-19 committees. This process appears to be driven primarily by the institutional settings of parliaments rather than by the characteristics or performance of Covid-19 crisis governance. Interestingly, this general pattern seems consistent across parliaments, regardless of the territorial-institutional level they represent. Despite substantial differences in parliamentary jurisdictions across territorial-institutional levels and

countries—both under normal circumstances and during the Covid-19 crisis—the institutional regulations in place appear to be the key factor shaping the formation of ad hoc Covid-19 committees.

VII. Conclusion

This study examined the ex-post legislative oversight of Covid-19 crisis governance in Europe through the establishment of ad hoc Covid-19 committees. To explain the formation of these committees, I first argued that radical right populist parties play a key role in driving their creation, seeking to politicize Covid-19 crisis governance and capitalize on growing public frustration with various Covid-19 measures. Additionally, assuming that opposition parties are the primary actors most invested in conducting an ex-post review of Covid-19 crisis governance, I proposed that ad hoc Covid-19 committees are more likely to be established when institutional rules provide greater opportunities for opposition parties and when the regulations governing their formation are less restrictive.

To test these hypotheses, I conducted a systematic search for ad hoc Covid-19 committees across the European Parliament, the lower and upper chambers of national legislatures in 33 European countries, and 98 regional legislatures in Austria, Belgium, Germany, Italy, Spain, Switzerland, and the UK, as well as six legislatures of autonomous communities and regions in Finland, France, Denmark, and Portugal. As of November 2024, these legislatures had established 49 ad hoc Covid-19 committees.

This analysis highlights that ad hoc committees are an empirically significant aspect of ex-post oversight of Covid-19 crisis governance. The findings show that the European Parliament, nearly one-third of national legislatures, and 31 percent of the regional legislatures included in the study established ad hoc Covid-19 committees, underscoring their relevance in legislative responses to the crisis.

Furthermore, I gathered previously unavailable data on the characteristics of ad hoc committees, to be able to assess the impact of institutional features on the establishment of such committees. The findings from the estimated multilevel model analyses indicate that the institutional characteristics of parliaments play a significant role in facilitating the formation of ad hoc committees. Specifically, parliaments with the authority to establish inquiry committees and those requiring a lower proportion of MPs to vote in favor of forming ad hoc Covid-19 committees are more likely to establish these committees. While radical right populist parties often vocally demand the creation of inquiry committees and a general review of Covid-19 crisis governance in certain countries and regions, the results show no significant association between the presence of radical right populist parties in the opposition and the formation of ad hoc Covid-19 committees.

Moreover, the features and outcomes of Covid-19 crisis governance do not appear to influence the formation patterns of ad hoc Covid-19 committees, according to the analysis results. The lack of association between the characteristics of Covid-19 crisis governance and the formation of these committees may be attributed to the significant diversity in their scope and focus. While some committees concentrated narrowly on the situation of specific social groups and specific crisis measures, others addressed broader agendas encompassing multiple aspects of the pandemic and its management.

This study's strength lies in its comprehensive mapping and analysis of the institutional rules governing ad hoc committees at the EU, national, and regional levels. However, the analyses presented also face certain limitations. First, the available cross-national data on the features, performance, and outcomes of Covid-19 crisis management—such as the Oxford Coronavirus Government Response Tracker and the Pandemic Backsliding dataset—primarily assess Covid-19 governance at the national level. There is a significant need for regional-level data on Covid-19 crisis governance to better understand the regional patterns in the formation of ad hoc Covid-19 committees.

Second, while this study provides new insights into the dynamics of ex-post parliamentary oversight of Covid-19 crisis governance, it is important to acknowledge that other forms of parliamentary oversight also played significant roles and should be addressed in future research. This study focused on ad hoc Covid-19 committees, but beyond these, permanent committees and their subcommittees—whether permanent or special—were integral to ex-post oversight. For instance, the Swiss Federal Parliament's Control Committees of the National Council and the Council of States were authorized to investigate the Covid-19 crisis responses of public authorities. These committees jointly identified several issues for inquiry, focusing on topics that were the subject of significant public debate.

Additionally, parliaments without the authority to form inquiry or study committees also made innovative efforts to establish new mechanisms for crisis oversight. For example, the Danish Parliament, which lacks the authority to establish inquiry commissions, commissioned an independent investigation into Covid-19 crisis governance in May 2020. This investigation was conducted by a committee of five professors with expertise in virology, immunology, law, economics, public administration, and political science. The initiative, commissioned by the Standing Orders Committee, was unprecedented in Danish parliamentary history and has been described as an “institutional innovation” and a response to debates about strengthening parliamentary oversight (Folketinget, 2021: 9). Furthermore, the Danish Parliament established a permanent Epidemics Committee to scrutinize ministers' application of provisions in the Epidemics Act. Some national and regional parliaments also opted to form subcommittees to investigate Covid-19 crisis governance. For example, in the canton of Zurich, the Control Committee and the Finance Committee collaborated to establish

a joint subcommittee to review the cantonal government's emergency responses. These examples highlight the diverse approaches parliaments have taken to adapt their oversight mechanisms to the challenges of the Covid-19 crisis, underscoring the importance of examining a broader spectrum of parliamentary oversight tools in future research.

Furthermore, this study excludes public inquiry commissions initiated by governments from its analysis, as the focus is on ex-post parliamentary oversight of Covid-19 crisis governance. Notably, public inquiry commissions were established by the Norwegian, Scottish, Swedish, and UK governments to review policy outcomes. Like some legislative study commissions, these public inquiry commissions often included experts and stakeholders. Additionally, some governments conducted internal evaluations or hired external consulting firms to assess their performance in managing the Covid-19 crisis. For example, in Switzerland, many regional executives and federal authorities engaged consulting firms to evaluate their Covid-19 responses. Similarly, the French government commissioned a group of experts to investigate its Covid-19 crisis governance in June 2020 (Le Monde, 2020).

Three avenues for future research appear particularly promising. First, future studies should examine in greater detail the opportunities that ad hoc committees provide to opposition parties. A more fine-grained analysis could uncover how these committees serve as tools for oppositional influence and scrutiny. Second, future research should address the role of the government-opposition divide and political polarization in the formation of ad hoc committees. Anecdotal evidence suggests that in Italy's and Spain's regional parliaments, the creation of ad hoc Covid-19 committees was driven by significant government-opposition divides and polarization. This divide is also relevant in evaluating the outcomes and recommendations of ad hoc Covid-19 committees, as it is unlikely that deeply divided committees produced substantive recommendations for improving future crisis governance. Finally, an additional task for future research will be to investigate the broader impact of ad hoc Covid-19 committees on governance, accountability, and policy learning.

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Appendix

Appendix A. Overview of legislative ad hoc Covid-19 commissions in Europe

Country	Territory	level	Parliamentarian chamber	Name of the committee	Type	First meeting of the ad hoc committee
EU	EU	EU	European Parliament	Special Committee on COVID-19 of the European Parliament	special	10.03.2022
Belgium	Belgium	national	House of Representatives	Commission Spéciale COVID-19	special	25.06.2020
Belgium	Vlaamse Gemeenschap	regional	Vlaamse Gemeenschap	Commissie ad hoc voor de Evaluatie en Verdere Uitvoering van het Vlaamse Coronabeleid	special	27.05.2020
Belgium	Deutsche Gemeinschaft	regional	Deutsche Gemeinschaft	Sonderausschuss zur Aufarbeitung der COVID-19-Pandemie und der Folgen der diesbezüglich getroffenen Maßnahmen in der Deutschsprachigen Gemeinschaft	special	20.07.2020
Belgium	Région wallonne	regional	Région wallonne	Commission spéciale chargée d'évaluer la gestion de la crise sanitaire de la Covid-19 par la Wallonie (2019-2024)	special	15.07.2020
Belgium	Brussels Gewest/Bruxelles-Région	regional	Brussels Gewest/Bruxelles-Région	Commission spéciale Covid 19/bijzondere commissie COVID-19	special	25.09.2020
Bulgaria	Bulgaria	national	National Assembly	ВРЕМЕННА КОМИСИЯ ЗА КОНТРОЛ НА РАЗХОДИТЕ НА ПУБЛИЧНИ СРЕДСТВА, СВЪРЗАНИ С ПРЕОДОЛЯВАНЕТО НА ПОСЛЕДСТВИЯТА ОТ РАЗПРОСТРАНЕНИЕТО НА КОВИД-19	inquiry	14.05.2020
Czech Republic	Czech Republic	national	Chamber of Deputies	Dočasná komise pro hodnocení účinnosti vládní pomoci v rámci COVID (Temporary Commission to Evaluate the Effectiveness of Government Assistance under COVID)	special	03.07.2020

France	France	national	National Assembly	Commission d'enquête pour mesurer et prévenir les effets de la crise du covid-19 sur les enfants et la jeunesse	inquiry	17.03.2020
France	France	national	Senate	Commission d'enquête pour l'évaluation des politiques publiques face aux grandes pandémies à la lumière de la crise sanitaire de la Covid-19 et de sa gestion	inquiry	01.07.2020
Germany	Baden-Württemberg	regional	Landtag Baden-Württemberg	Enquetekommission „Krisenfeste Gesellschaft“	special	07.02.2022
Germany	Bavaria	regional	Bayerischer Landtag	Untersuchungsausschuss Maske	inquiry	15.10.2021
Germany	Brandenburg	regional	Landtag Brandenburg	Untersuchung der Krisenpolitik der Landesregierung im Zusammenhang mit dem Coronavirus SARS-CoV-2 und der Erkrankung COVID-19	inquiry	23.09.2020
Germany	Lower Saxony	regional	Niedersächsischer Landtag	Sonderausschuss zur Aufarbeitung der bisher gewonnenen Erkenntnisse aus der Bekämpfung der COVID-19-Pandemie und - daraus schlussfolgernd - zur Vorbereitung auf künftige pandemiebedingte Gesundheits- und Wirtschaftskrisen	special	06.10.2020
Germany	North Rhine-Westphalia	regional	Landtag Nordrhein-Westfalen	Enquetekommission II „Krisen- und Notfallmanagement“ – durch die Lehren der Vergangenheit die Zukunft sicher gestalten	special	26.05.2023
Germany	Rhineland-Palatinate	regional	Landtag Rheinland-Pfalz	Enquete-Kommission „Vorsorge- und Bekämpfungsmaßnahmen gegen die Ausbreitung des Coronavirus in Rheinland-Pfalz und Konsequenzen für die Pandemiepolitik“	special	27.05.2020
Ireland	Ireland	national	House of Representatives	Special Committee on Covid-19 Response	special	06.05.2020
Italy	Italy	national	Chamber of Deputies	Commissione parlamentare di inchiesta sulla gestione dell'emergenza sanitaria causata dalla diffusione epidemica del virus SARS-CoV-2 e sulle misure adottate per prevenire e affrontare l'emergenza epidemiologica da SARS-CoV-2	inquiry	22.03.2024

Italy	Liguria	regional	Regional Council	Commissione speciale con funzione di inchiesta sulla gestione dell'emergenza sanitaria conseguente al contagio Covid-19	inquiry	03.06.2020
Italy	Lombardy	regional	Regional Council	Commissione d'inchiesta - Emergenza Covid-19	inquiry	13.05.2020
Italy	Tuscany	regional	Regional Council	Commissione speciale supporto, monitoraggio e controllo campagna vaccinale prevenzione infezioni da SARS-CoV-2	special	05.05.2021
Italy	Tuscany	regional	Regional Council	Commissione d'inchiesta verifica corretto svolgimento misure messe in atto dal sistema sanitario regionale per contrastare pandemia da Covid-19	inquiry	10.01.2022
Italy	Umbria	regional	Assemblea Legislativa	Commissione d'inchiesta sulla gestione dell'emergenza sanitaria durante la pandemia da Covid-19	inquiry	23.03.2021
Italy	Veneto	regional	Regional Council	Commissione speciale d'inchiesta sull'andamento in Veneto dei contagi e dei decessi da SARS-CoV-2 durante la pandemia con particolare attenzione alla seconda "ondata"	inquiry	28.05.2020
Latvia	Latvia	national	Parliament	Parlamentārās izmeklēšanas komisija, lai izmeklētu Latvijas valdības kļūdaino rīcību Covid-19 pandēmijas pārvarēšanas procesā, kā arī nosauktu to politisko amatpersonu vārdus, kuras izraisījušas neatgriezeniski negatīvas sekas Latvijai	inquiry	08.04.2021
Netherlands	Netherlands	national	House of Representatives	Tijdelijke commissie Corona	inquiry	06.02.2024
Portugal	Azores	regional	Legislative Assembly of the Azores	Comissão de Inquérito à Operacionalização das Agendas Mobilizadoras	inquiry	19.11.2021
Portugal	Madeira	regional	Legislative Assembly of Madeira	Comissão de Inquérito sobre «As falhas na operacionalização da linha de crédito às empresas da Região Autónoma da Madeira afetadas pelo surto do novo coronavírus (COVID-19), designada linha de crédito INVEST RAM»	inquiry	19.05.2022
Romania	Romania	national	Chamber of Deputies	Comisia parlamentară de anchetă privind achizițiile publice efectuate în sectorul sanitar în timpul stărilor de urgență și de alertă pe teritoriul României	inquiry	03.11.2021

Slovenia	Slovenia	national	National Assembly	Preiskovalna komisija o zagotavljanju zaščitne opreme ter ukrepov institucij in nosilcev javnih funkcij za zajezitev širjenja bolezni COVID-19 od 1. 2. 2020	inquiry	29.09.2020
Slovenia	Slovenia	national	National Assembly	Preiskovalna komisija o ugotavljanju morebitne politične odgovornosti nosilcev javnih funkcij za finančno neustrezne ukrepe in sum neupravičenega omejevanja pravic pri izvajanju ukrepov, povezanih z epidemijo nalezljive bolezni COVID-19	inquiry	20.11.2020
Spain	Spain	national	Congress of Deputies	Comisión de Investigación relativa a la gestión de las vacunas y el Plan de Vacunación en España	inquiry	24.06.2021
Spain	Spain	national	Congress of Deputies	Comisión de Investigación sobre los hechos, responsabilidades y enseñanzas en torno a los procesos de contratación para la adquisición de material sanitario por parte de las Administraciones públicas durante la crisis pandémica ocasionada por la COVID-19	inquiry	02.04.2024
Spain	Andalucia	regional	La Junta	Comisión de estudio sobre la recuperación económica y social de Andalucía a causa de la pandemia del COVID-19	study	24.04.2020
Spain	Cantabria	regional	Parlamento de Cantabria	Comisión especial no permanente para el estudio y seguimiento del Covid-19	study	11.04.2020
Spain	Castilla-La Mancha	regional	Cortes de la Castilla-la Mancha	Comisión no Permanente de Estudio sobre la gestión y efectos del COVID-19 en Castilla-La Mancha	study	23.07.2020
Spain	Castilla y León	regional	Cortes de Castilla y León	Comisión de Investigación relativa a la incidencia del COVID-19 en las residencias en Castilla y León	inquiry	24.09.2021
Spain	Catalunya/Cataluña	regional	Parlamento de Cataluña	Comissió d'Estudi de la Reconstrucció i la Reactivació Socials i Econòmiques	study	07.07.2020
Spain	Extremadura	regional	Asamblea de Extremadura	Comisión no Permanente de Estudio (CNPE-4), sobre la Pandemia del COVID-19 en el ámbito de la Comunidad Autónoma de Extremadura	study	06.05.2020
Spain	Galiza/Galicia	regional	Parlamento de Galicia	Comisión no permanente especial de estudio sobre la reactivación económica, social y cultural de Galicia por la crisis de la Covid-19	study	21.09.2020

Spain	La Rioja	regional	Parlamento de la Rioja	Comisión de investigación para aclarar la adquisición material sanitario	inquiry	01.02.2023
Spain	La Rioja	regional	Parlamento de la Rioja	Comisión estudio para recuperación económica-social tras crisis COVID-19	study	29.05.2020
Spain	Madrid	regional	Asamblea de Madrid	Comisión de Investigación sobre la situación provocada por el COVID-19 en los centros residenciales de personas mayores de la Comunidad de Madrid y la gestión que hizo el Gobierno Regional de la misma durante los meses de febrero a junio de 7439-7440 2020	inquiry	06.07.2020
Spain	Melilla	regional	Asamblea de Melilla	Comisión Especial de la Asamblea para la Covid-19	special	02.10.2020
Spain	Principo de Asturias	regional	Junta General del Principo de Asturias	Comisión de Estudio de la gestión de la crisis sanitaria COVID-19	study	13.05.2020
Spain	Région de Murcia	regional	Asamblea Regional de Murcia	Comisión Especial de Estudio sobre el Plan de Reactivación Económica y Social, y de Evaluación del Impacto del Coronavirus en la Región de Murcia	special	18.05.2020
United Kingdom	United Kingdom	national	House of Lords	COVID-19 Committee	special	01.07.2020
United Kingdom	Northern Ireland	regional	Tionól Thuaisceart Éireann	Ad Hoc Committee on the COVID-19 Response	special	31.03.2020
United Kingdom	Wales	regional	Senedd	Wales Covid-19 Inquiry Special Purpose Committee	inquiry	16.05.2023

Appendix B. Operationalization of the variables

Dependent variable	Operationalization	Source
Ad hoc Covid-19 committee	Establishment of ad hoc committee within a legislative cycle Dummy variable: 1: yes; 0: no	Own data collection
Independent variables		
Radical right populist parties' presence in opposition	Dummy variable: 1: presence in opposition; 0: not in opposition	Own data collection
Required support	Share of MPs required for the establishment of an ad hoc committee	Own data collection
Authority to establish inquiry committees	Dummy variable 1: yes; 0: no	Own data collection
Authority to establish study committees	Dummy variable 1: yes; 0: no	Own data collection
Oppositional opportunities	Index of three variables: 1) Presidency or vice-presidency of an inquiry or special committee is reserved for oppositional parties 2) Possibility to reflect minority opinion in the final report of an inquiry or special committee 3) Closed meetings of inquiry or special committees	Own data collection
Variables for robustness checks and alternative explanations		
Seat share of radical right populist parties	Seat share of radical right populist parties in the parliament	Own data collection relying on parliaments' websites
State of emergency	Declaration of some type of a state of emergency Dummy variable 1: yes; 0: no	Own data collection
Severity of the health crisis	Maximum monthly excess mortality	Eurostat database (demo_mexrt) https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/demo_mexrt__custom_8980386/default/table?lang=en
Stringency of Covid-19 crisis measures	Maximum of the additive index of the stringency of policy measures composed of the following individual policy response indicators: (1) restrictions on gatherings (0-4); (2) stay at home requirements (0-3); (3) restrictions on internal movement (0-2); (4) international travel controls (0-4).	Oxford Coronavirus Government Response Tracker (OxCGRT) project (Hale et al., 2021)

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Parliamentarian restrictions	<p>Maximum of the additive index of three variables:</p> <p>(1) the law requires that the national legislature approve the implementation of the legal instrument used as the main national-level response to Covid-19 (dummy variable);</p> <p>(2) the legislature has approved the implementation of the legal instrument as the main national response (dummy variable);</p> <p>3) the extent to which the lawmaking role of the legislature is limited due to any of the emergency measures taken with reference to the Covid-19 pandemic (Ordinal variable: 0-4).</p> <p>I adjusted the indicator to equalize their weights, ensuring the index ranges from 0 to 3, where higher values indicate a more constrained role of the legislature in governing the Covid-19 crisis. In countries where the state-wide legislature established an ad hoc Covid-19 committee, the maximum value is calculated from March 11th, 2020, up to the quarter preceding the formation of the relevant committee's inaugural meeting. In countries without an ad hoc Covid-19 committee, the maximal value was taken until the end of the relevant legislative cycle.</p>	Variables emleglaw, emlegapp and leglimit from the Pandemic Backsliding (PanDem) project by the V-Dem Institute (Edgell et al., 2020)
Control variables		
Size of parliament	Number of MPs in a parliament	Own data collection
Cycle length	Number of days of a legislative cycle	Own data collection
Past ad hoc Covid-19 committees	Dummy variable: 1: if in a previous legislative cycle an ad hoc Covid-19 committee was present	Own data collection

Appendix C. Conceptualization of oppositional opportunities in ad hoc committees

The independent variable in hypothesis 3 evaluates the opportunities of oppositional parties within ad hoc commissions. The index is developed drawing on previous studies conceptualizing and measuring oppositional parties' powers in parliamentary committees. It is constructed as an index comprising five components. Firstly, whether the **presidency or the vice-presidency of the ad hoc committee** is reserved for an oppositional party. The presidency is important because it has agenda powers, leads hearings etc and it also receives more publicity (Garritzmann, 2017: 11; Mattson, and Strøm, 1995: 277; Strøm, 1990: 71; Wegmann 2022: 9). While the overwhelming majority of the parliaments distribute ad hoc commission membership according to the seat share of parliamentary group, there is a considerable variation with regard to the distribution of the presidency and vice-presidency of the committees to the oppositional parties. This component is a dummy variable if the presidency or vice-presidency is reserved for an oppositional party 1 and otherwise 0.

Secondly, it considers the possibility to submit **a minority report or to document minority opinions in the final report** within the commission (Mattson, and Strøm, 1995: 283-284; Wegmann, 2022: 9). This component is a dummy variable takes the value 1 if the minority opinions and reports can be submitted and otherwise 0.

Finally, I assess whether **meetings are open to the public or held behind closed doors** (Garritzmann, 2017: 11). Accordingly, the resulting variable is coded as follows: a value of 0 indicates that ad hoc committee meetings are generally held behind closed doors, 1 indicates that such meetings are generally public, and 0.5 is assigned when the meetings are typically closed but hearings are public. Closed meetings are considered advantageous for opposition parties, as it is assumed that more information is shared and gathered in a confidential setting (Strøm, 1998).

The "opportunities in the committee system" is the mean of these three items, which thus again varies between 1 (many opportunities) and 0 (no opportunities).

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Appendix D. Selection of radical right populist parties

Country	Abbr.	Party name in original language	Party name in English
Austria	FPÖ	Freiheitliche Partei Österreichs	Freedom Party of Austria
Belgium	VB	Vlaams Belang	Flemish Interest
Bulgaria	Vazrazhdane	Vazrazhdane	Revival
Croatia	Hrast	Hrvatski rast	Croatian Growth
	HS	Hrvatski suverenisti	Croatian Sovereignists
	DP*	Domovinski pokret	Homeland Movement
Cyprus	ELAM	Ethniko Laiko Metopo	National Popular Front
Czech Republic	SPD*	Svoboda a přímá demokracie	Freedom and Direct Democracy
Denmark	DF	Dansk Folkeparti	Danish People's Party
	NB	Nye Borgerlige	The New Allright
Estonia	EKRE	Eesti Konservatiivne Rahvaerakond	Conservative People's Party of Estonia
Finland	PS	Suomen Maaseudun Puolue Perussuomalaiset	Finns Party
France	FN	Front National	National Front
	UXD*	Union de l'extrême droite	Union of the Far-Right
Germany	AfD	Alternative für Deutschland	Alternative for Germany
Greece	EL	Elliniki Lisi	Greek Solution
	Spartans*	Spartiátes	Spartans
Hungary	Fidesz-KDNP	Fidesz-KDNP	Fidesz-KDNP
	Jobbik	Jobbik Magyarországért Mozgalom	Movement for a Better Hungary
Iceland	none		
Ireland	none		
Italy	Lega	Lega	
	Fdi	Fratelli di Italia	Brothers of Italy
Latvia	NA	Nacionālā Apvienība	National Alliance
Liechtenstein	none		
Lithuania	TT	Tvarka ir teisingumas	Order and Justice
Luxembourg	none		
Malta	none		
	none		
Netherlands	PVV	Partij voor de Vrijheid	Party for Freedom
	FvD	Forum voor Democratie	Forum for Democracy
Norway	FrP	Fremskrittspartiet	Progress Party
Poland	PiS	Prawo i Sprawiedliwość	Law and Justice
	Confederation	Konfederacja (KORWIN, Ruch Narodowy, Konfederacja Korony Polskiej)	Confederation alliance (New Hope, National Movement, Confederation of the Polish Crown)
Portugal	CHEGA	CHEGA	Enough
Romania	AUR*	Alianța AUR	AUR Alliance
Slovakia	L'SNS	Kotlebovci – Ľudová strana naše Slovensk	Kotlebists – People's Party Our Slovakia

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Slovenia	SNS	Slovenska Nacionalna Stranka	Slovenian National Party
Sweden	SD	Sverigedemokraterna	Sweden Democrats
Switzerland	SVP	Schweizerische Volkspartei	Swiss People's Party
	Lega	Lega dei Ticinesi	Ticino League
Spain	Vox	Vox	Voice
United Kingdom		UKIP	UKIP
*New party not in PopuList (Rooduijn et al., 2024) included			

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Appendix E. Summary statistics of the variables

Ad hoc Covid-19 committee	Freq.	Percent
0	236	82.81
1	49	17.19
Total	285	100.00

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. dev.	Min	Max
Required support	272	.4378513	.1167494	.0833333	.51
Size of parliament	285	123.6491	127.1701	21	800
Cycle length	282	1218.582	509.1097	29	2191

Radical right populist parties' presence in opposition	Freq.	Percent
0	167	58.60
1	118	41.40
Total	285	100.00

Inquiry committee	Freq.	Percent
0	42	14.74
1	243	85.26
Total	285	100.00

Study committee	Freq.	Percent
0	192	67.37
1	93	32.63
Total	285	100.00

Subnational region	Freq.	Percent
0	96	33.68
1	189	66.32
Total	285	100.00

Past ad hoc Covid-19 committees	Freq.	Percent
0	254	89.12
1	31	10.88
Total	285	100.00

Appendix F. Results of two-level logit regression models of establishment of ad hoc Covid-19 commissions including regional, national and EU-level parliaments (only lower chambers of national legislatures)

	A1	A2	A3	A4	A5	A6
Radical right populist opposition	0.447 (0.40)				0.317 (0.43)	0.225 (0.48)
Inquiry committee		2.488* (1.24)			2.248 (1.32)	2.567 (1.49)
Study committee			0.134 (0.49)			
Required support				-5.691* (2.53)	-5.130* (2.59)	-5.680 (2.92)
Parliament size						0.004 (0.00)
Past ad hoc Covid-19 committee						-1.426 (0.81)
Regional parliament						0.651 (0.95)
Length of legislative cycle						0.001* (0.00)
Constant	-2.151*** (0.46)	-4.104*** (1.24)	-1.964*** (0.42)	0.524 (1.12)	-1.881 (1.71)	-4.506* (2.27)
<i>Variance component</i>						
Country-level	1.760 (1.21)	1.740 (1.13)	1.785 (1.19)	2.529 (1.61)	2.716 (1.75)	4.355 (2.75)
N observations	270	270	270	264	264	263
N countries	33	33	33	33	33	33
Log-likelihood	-114.244	-111.82	-114.82	-110.726	-108.349	-96.625

Dependent variable: Establishment of an ad hoc Covid-19 committee;

* p<0.05, ** p<0.01, *** p<0.001, Standard errors in parentheses

